

Non-destructive evaluation of micro cracking in short fibre reinforced thermoplastics with X-ray-refraction

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SUMMARY

Short fibre reinforced thermoplastic materials are increasing by used in automotive applications. The knowledge of the long term behaviour due to mechanical and environmental loading is important to assure the reliability of structural elements. The X-Ray-Refraction technique enables non-destructively the evaluation of inner surfaces especially in composite materials. Hence, the residual strength reduction could be correlated with the increase of micro cracking due to mechanical and environmental loading.

Keywords: short fibre reinforced composites, NDT, X-ray-Refraction, micro cracking

MATERIALS CHARACTERIZATION

X-ray-refraction topography [1] is caused by the effect of refraction at the interface of different materials, each having its specific refractive index as well known from visible light passing glass lenses. In the case of X-rays the refraction angle is below half a degree and in opposite direction due to the dispersion function of isolators. In the experimental set-up a collimated X-ray beam passes the sample. At a fixed angle the refracted signal is measured and additionally a signal proportional to the absorption. A characteristic refraction value C is determined, which is proportional to the inner surface per unit volume. The intensity of the refracted beam will increase if the difference of the refractive index rises at the observed interfaces. Hence the intensity will be higher for materials with debonded fibres or pores than without (Fig. 1 left). By calibration the real as well as the relative inner surfaces are measured. The relative increase is sufficient in most cases and used in further investigations. Scanning the whole area of the sample gives a topographic map of inner surfaces (Fig. 1 right). In figure 2 an X-ray-refraction principle is shown.

Fig. 1: X-ray-refraction – effects and topography

Fig. 2: X-ray-refraction principle

EXPERIMENTAL

The intralaminar fatigue behaviour of continuous fibre reinforced materials was comprehensively investigated with the X-ray-refraction technique in [2]. Additionally the statistical character of the failure behaviour under intralaminar transverse and shear loading were studied by applying the X-ray-refraction technique online mechanical loading [3],[4]. Further on the damage accumulation of short fibre reinforced thermoplastic matrix material was investigated by [5].

The materials are a short glass fibre reinforced polyoxymethylene (POM) and a short glass fibre reinforced polybutylenterephthalat (PBT). Injection moulded samples have been prepared by Ticona GmbH according to [6]. The glass fibre (E-glass) part is 26wt.%, the mean fibre length is $320\mu\text{m}$ and the fibre diameter $10\pm 1\mu\text{m}$. Selane compounds are used for fibre adhesion dressing.

In the present paper the durability of thermoplastics is discussed. The first section gives an impression of results of the non-destructive X-ray-refraction technique. Therefore long term behaviour of short glass fibre reinforced PBT under creep 3-point-bending loading is described. The second section discusses the damage of short term loading in tensile tests on short fibre reinforced POM compared with continuous fibre reinforced materials. The third section points out long term tension and fatigue behaviour of short fibre reinforced POM. Finally, investigation on aging of short fibre reinforced PBT and POM is presented. In all figures each point represents an average of at least three measurements.

The long term behaviour of short glass fibre reinforced PBT under creep 3-point-bending was investigated. In the 3-point-bending experiment the increase of the X-ray refraction value is caused by micro cracking. Micro-cracking in the polymer matrix occurs at the end of short glass fibres, due to the fibre orientation in length direction of the sample and the stress state. Hence, the stress state is mapped by the increase of inner surfaces with increasing time of creep loading (Fig. 3 right). An X-ray-refraction system is shown in figure 3 (left).

Fig. 3: X-ray-refraction system and X-ray-refraction topography - 3-point-bending-creep

A short glass fibre reinforced POM was used to investigate the damage under short term loading in tensile tests. The X-ray-refraction technique can be applied online and offline. Online, refraction values (inner surface; micro crack density) can be measured without unloading the specimen. Secondly, a specimen can be loaded and unloaded in any other test system and the unloaded specimen is measured offline. Due to the closing of some micro cracks, X-ray-refraction technique gives not the same value (Fig. 4 left). The characteristic of the increase remains the same. When they reach the highest global refraction value, specimens macroscopically fracture in the region of the highest local refraction value.

Fig. 4: micro cracks - tensile tests

Micro cracks that are aligned in different directions can be quantified in an offline measurement. The ratio between micro cracks orientated perpendicular and parallel to

load is around 2.3 (Fig. 4 right). Due to the high orientation of fibres the damage is caused more by matrix-cracks and fibre-matrix-interface-cracks of fibres oriented perpendicular to load than fibre-matrix-interface-cracks of fibres oriented parallel to load.

The increase of micro cracks in continuous fibre reinforced materials is discussed in [3],[4]. Continuous fibre reinforced materials can be loaded until the micro crack density is saturated of (Fig. 5). The increase can be statistically described with a Weibull-distribution. Used laminates are made of $0^\circ/90^\circ$ or $\pm 45^\circ$ plies. Plies next to a damaged ply support weak regions and an overcritical loading is possible. A short fibre reinforced material fails without saturation (Fig. 6).

Fig. 5: micro cracks - tensile tests

Fig. 6: micro cracks - tensile tests

An increase of inner surface represents a progressing damage. This damage is coupled to a decrease of residual strength. Each refraction value, caused by micro cracks perpendicular and parallel to load, characterizes a correlation in a uniform manner between refraction value and residual strength (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7: correlation of micro cracks and residual strength - tensile tests

Fig. 8: micro cracks - creep tests

Micro cracks occur, due to long term tension of short glass fibre reinforced POM. This micro crack damage correlates with the loading time (Fig. 8). Each refraction value, caused by micro cracks perpendicular and parallel to load, increases with loading time.

Fatigue loading of short glass fibre reinforced POM causes micro cracks. The state of damage is characterized by the micro crack density represented by the refraction value. Cracks oriented perpendicular and parallel to load likewise increase with every load cycle (Fig. 9 left). The residual strength correlates with both refraction values (Fig. 9 right).

Fig. 9: micro cracks and correlation of micro cracks and residual strength - fatigue tests

In the aging test of short glass fibre reinforced PBT in hot water (98°C), the X-ray-refraction topography gives an increase of fibre matrix debonding due to the aging of the interface (Fig. 10 left). Hence, the strength of the material decreases with increasing time and fibre matrix debonding. The residual strength is in good correlation with the refraction value (Fig. 10 right).

Fig. 10: micro cracks and correlation of micro cracks and residual strength - aging tests

Fig. 11: micro cracks and correlation of micro cracks and residual strength - aging tests

Short glass fibre reinforced POM was aged by artificial weathering in light and moisture regarding to [7]. After 2000h of exposure the micro cracking extremely increased (Fig. 11 left). As much as the state of micro cracking and damage increases, the residual strength decreases (Fig. 11 right).

CONCLUSIONS

X-ray-refraction topography is caused by the effect of refraction at the interface of different materials, each having its specific refractive index. A characterization of damage accumulation was made by using this non-destructive evaluation of micro cracking in short fibre reinforced thermoplastics. Short term tensile tests, long term

creep tests and fatigue tests were used to describe the features and correlations of micro cracking. Micro cracks perpendicular and parallel to load increase in the same manner, leading to a dimensionless description. Due to the leak of supporting plies, like in continuous fibre reinforced laminates with different ply orientations, no saturation of micro crack density occurs in short term loading of short fibre reinforced thermoplastics. Aging by hot water and artificial weathering result in micro crack damage. In general, micro crack damage represented by refraction values is correlated with residual strength. Independent of the load history or aging history, an increasing micro crack density decreases the residual strength.

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References

1. Reference Hentschel, M.P., Harbich, K.-W., Lange, A.: „Non-destructive evaluation of single fibre debonding in composites by X-ray refraction“, NDT&E International, Vol. 27, 5 (1994) p. 275
2. Trappe, V., Harbich, K.-W., Ernst, H.: „Intralaminar fatigue behaviour of carbon fibre reinforced plastics“; Int. Journal of Fatigue 28 (2006) 1187-1196
3. Trappe, V., Ivers, H.: “Determination of Inter-Fibre-Failure in Complex, Reinforced Composites”, proceedings of the 16th European Conference of Fracture, Alexandroupolis, Greece 2006, Springer, ISBN 1-4020-4971-4
4. Trappe, V., Hickmann, S., Sturm, H.: „Bestimmung des Zwischenfaserbruchversagens in textilverstärktem Glasfaserkunststoff mittels der Röntgenrefrations-topografie“, MP Materials Testing 50 (2008) 10, 615-622
5. Rudolph, H.-V., Hentschel, M.-P., Ivers, H., Harbich, K.-W.: „Characterization of damage accumulation during fatigue in fibre reinforced thermoplast by X-ray-refraction“, Nondestructive Characterization of Materials XI, Springer (2003), ISBN 354040154-7
6. DIN EN ISO 527, “Determination of tensile properties”, 1996
7. DIN EN ISO 4892-3 “Methods of exposure to laboratory light sources – Part 3: Fluorescent UV lamps”, 2006